

An algebraic vs. transcendent approach to Legendre module and Feigenbaum constants

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Abstract:

Legendre module λ , Feigenbaum constant δ_F and α_F and modular units $g(u)$ depend on principal ideals of complex multiplication (CM). The Hermite problem for cubic irrationalities is treated by quaternary continued fractions (QCF). Point addition on elliptic curves is generalized to CM via QCF showing λ - invariances and a tower of modular units $g(u)$. Statistical λ - fluctuations on d - dimensional hypersurfaces S_d ($d \leq 5$) shape a pseudo- periodic contour C_M . A transcendent vs. algebraic treatment of δ_F , α_F and λ depends on topological entropy of C_M . Cycles on disk segments S_d yield $\delta_F \alpha_F^2 = const$ in agreement with computation.

1.Introduction

Invariants of an elliptic curve E_λ are algebraic number lying in $\mathbb{K}(\partial)$ for a non-trivial endomorphism

$\text{End}(E_\lambda/\mathbb{K}) \cong \{M \in \mathbb{C} : M\mathbb{L} \subset \mathbb{L}\} \neq \mathbb{Z}$ and a lattice $\mathbb{L} \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$ and cubic irrationality ∂

. Complex multiplication (CM) is singular if M belongs to an imaginary quadratic field $M \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$. Principal ideal domains discussed here with class number one

$h_\Delta=1$ exist only in cases $e_\Delta=(1,2,3)$ with discriminants

$\Delta=\{(7,1,19,43,67,163),4,3\}$.

The present paper calculates the Legendre module λ itself by an elliptic addition theorem with Poncelet closure [1].

The transcendental entire function

is independent on the path between endpoints of \mathcal{C}_{u_0} . Collineated quadruples

$$\wp_k \leftarrow \wp_{k-1} + a_{1k} \wp_{k-2} + a_{2k} \wp_{k-3} + a_{3k} \wp_{k-4} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{a})\{\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}, \wp_{k-4}\}$$

with $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{a})$ from (0.51) entering (0.47) yield CM layers with $M_d \in \mathbb{C}^d$ and complex

Legendre module $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$. As a statistical product of modular units $g(u)$ [2] λ depends

on the sum of \mathcal{C}_{u_0} . One-dimensional chaotic maps are transformed to point

addition generalizing [3]. Mandelbrot maps require d- dimensional complex spaces \mathbb{C}^d to picture cardioids. A complex parameter $c \in \mathbb{C}$ and complex Feigenbaum constants $\delta_F \in \mathbb{C}$ is related to complex λ .

For a normal field $\mathbb{N}[\sqrt{\Delta}] = \mathbb{K}[\partial]\mathbb{K}'[\partial]\mathbb{K}''[\partial]$ in case of $h_\Delta = 1$ and $e_\Delta = (1,2,3)$ invariants $j \in \mathbb{N}$ are reducible to a cubic polynomial

$$f^3(\omega) + 2Ef^2(\omega) + 2Ff(\omega) + 2 = 0 \quad (0.1)$$

for the Weber- Schlaefli invariant $f(\omega) = 1^{\frac{-1}{48}} \frac{\eta(\frac{\omega+1}{2})}{\eta(\omega)}$ [4] with Dedekind eta

function $\eta(\omega)$, Weber invariant $\gamma_2 = \sqrt[3]{j} = \frac{f^{24}(\omega) - 2^4}{f^8(\omega)} \in \mathbb{N}$ and integers $(E F) =$

$(0,0), (1,1), (0,-1), (1,0), (1,-1), (3,2) \in \mathbb{N}^2$. The square of the Dedekind eta function

$\eta^2(\omega) = \frac{\text{P}g(a\omega)}{\text{P}g(a'\omega)}$ depends on an infinity of representations in terms modular

units (0.12). This allows a Hermite substitution of (0.1) being quadratic $f \rightarrow f^2$ and modular for a field with $h_\Delta = 1$.

A cycle with $f^{b^{2^k}}(\omega) = 1$ has complex k roots at $k_{CS} = H_{CS} + \frac{2\pi i n}{\ln 3}$ where

$H_{CS} = \log_3 2$ is the Hausdorff dimension of Cantor set, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, with generator b^{2^k} with $b = 3^k = 2$ has roots of unity for first four prime Fermat number congruences [5].

Fluctuations of $f(\omega)$ for CM fields $M_d \mathbb{L}$ change λ and quarter periods $K(\lambda)$ and $K'(\lambda)$. Relations in (u, λ) variables are simpler [6]. In distinction, $K(\lambda)$ and $\lambda(K)$ descriptions get inequivalent statistically as fluctuations of a cubic $K(\lambda)$ equation leading to a linear $K \simeq \lambda$ relation on disk segments $S_d [M_d \mathbb{L}]$ of a generalized Riemann surface $\delta \mathbb{X}$:

First the N^{th} Landen transform of real values $K(\lambda)$ with Legendre module λ [7] yields

$$q = 1^{\frac{iK'}{2K}} = e^{2^{-N} \ln \lambda_N + 2^{2-N} \ln 2} \quad (0.2)$$

Here one has $\lambda(\delta \varphi) \rightarrow 0$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Poncelet closure with $u \in \mathbb{L}$ as point addition in \mathbb{L} with cycles, creates a CM field M inducing an iteration $K_{d+1}[\lambda_{d+1}]$ on S_{d+1} . The CM field arises from QCF and creates the iteration process

$$u[K_d[\lambda_d[g[u, M_d \mathbb{L}[K_{d-1}[\lambda_{d-1}[\dots]]]]]]] \in M \mathbb{L}_d .$$

The lattice recursion $\mathbb{L}_d[\mathbb{L}_{d-1}, \mathbb{L}_1]$ is equivalent to a d-dimensional representation of cardioids of Mandelbrot sets.

Fluctuating values $f(\omega)$ enter (0.2) via $\lambda\lambda' = 2^4/f^{24}(\omega)$ with $\lambda'=1-\lambda$. CM fields M_{d-1} are created itself as unimodular collineated points. In case of cycles (Poncelet closure) $\lambda(\delta\wp=\wp(u)-\wp(u'))$ depends on a product of modular units $g(u, \mathbb{L}_d)$ as a difference product of Weierstrass \wp - functions. The present paper discusses the complex case $\lambda(\delta\wp) \in \mathbb{C}$ for a pencil $\{E_\lambda\}$ with complex $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ with fluctuating complex $f(\omega)$ on $S_d [M_d\mathbb{L}]$. For a definite supremum algorithm λ is proportional to changes of topological entropy h_t . Accordingly, Legendre module and Feigenbaum constant get complex for cyclotomic and modular units on S^1 in dependence on powers $f^N(\omega)$. In this case a center of origin of \mathbb{C} develops where $\delta\mathbb{X}$ consists of nested disks.

$\lambda(\delta\wp)$ reads in terms of vol.1 p.210 [8] is given by integrals of third kind

$$\lambda(\delta\wp) = (ijkl) = \frac{(ij)(kl)}{(ik)(jl)} = \frac{\sigma_{ij}\sigma_{kl}}{\sigma_{ik}\sigma_{jl}} \quad (0.3)$$

where $\lambda'=1-\lambda$, $(ij)=p(u_i)-p(u_j)$, $p(u)=\gamma\wp(u)$, $\sigma_{ij} = \sigma(u_i+u_j)\sigma(u_i-u_j)$ and $\gamma \in GL(2, \mathbb{C})$. Its σ - dependence [1]

$$\lambda(\wp) = (p(u_1)p(u_2)p(u_3)p(u_4)) = e^{\int_C (ijkl)^{dv\zeta(v)}} \quad (0.4)$$

Is invariant with respect to $u_i \rightarrow u_s - u_i$ where $u_s = \frac{1}{2}(u_1+u_2+u_3+u_4)$.

$\lambda(\wp)$ depends only on endpoints of a 4-contour $C(ijkl)$

$$C(ijkl) = (u_i+u_k, u_i+u_j) \oplus (u_i-u_k, u_i-u_j) \oplus (u_j+u_l, u_k+u_l) \oplus (u_j-u_l, u_k-u_l)$$

which are shifted by $M(\mathbf{a})u$ and extended to an N -contour for a Poncelet N - Polygon.

$f(\omega)$, γ_2 and j are invariant for equivalent $\gamma \in SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$ $\omega \rightarrow \gamma\omega$. A shifted lattice $M_d\mathbb{L}$ is equivalent to a pseudo-periodic component at point addition yields $f(\omega) \rightarrow \gamma_\wp f(\omega)$ due to a fractional substitutions of roots. The aim of the present paper is to show that the exponent $\int dv\zeta$ of $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ depends on a value of the Legendre module itself via QCF which shift and add endpoints of $C(ijkl)$. The contour dependence of $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ leads to a Tschirnhaus resolvent set $\{f(\omega)\}$ of (0.1) [9] for complex $f(\omega)$ in $M_d\mathbb{L}$ with $d=1,2,3,4$. Then N - point addition is reducible to quadratic map and Legendre module $\lambda(\delta\wp)$ and elliptic (modular) unit $g(u, \mathbb{L})$ generalize Feigenbaum constants δ_F and α_F . The generalized principal ideal theorem of complex multiplication [10] predicts an equivalence $\lambda_N g^2(u, \mathbb{L}) \simeq \delta_F \alpha_F^2$ if a generator exists of a number theoretic transform as a tower of modular units.

The elliptic addition theorem is formulated as a matrix of fourth order suffering unimodular collineations as QCF.

2. Universal Covering

Corollary 1: A generalized Riemann surface $\delta\mathbb{X}$ is a Riemann surface \mathbb{X}_d of genus d reducible to a lattice of nested disks $S_d[M_d\mathbb{L}]$ of tori layers \mathbb{X}_1 having $\binom{d-2}{2}$ independent parameter for $d \leq 5$. $\delta\mathbb{X}$ consists of k iterated rational self-maps from S_d to nested spheres $S^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ with $i=1, \dots, g$, $\mathbf{a}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and p_i - the power of a point of origin with respect to the sphere. Iteration index k gets complex within a d -dimensional complex space $S_d \in \mathbb{C}^g$ with poles $u_p \notin \mathbb{Q}M_d\mathbb{L}$. Uniformization u_k is minimal four-component where $u_k \simeq \sum_{d=1, \dots, 5} (f^3(\omega) - \overline{f^3(\omega)}) u_k^{(d)} + \lambda_3 \chi(E)$ caused by fluctuations of (0.1) where $u_k^{(d)} \in \mathbb{C}^d$ using (0.22).

Proof: Periodic cycles of a map are cyclotomic units continuable to modular units on lattice positions. A disk segment $S_d[M_d\mathbb{L}]$ embedded in lattice $M_d\mathbb{L}$ is equivalent to a cardioid of a Mandelbrot set which can be uniformized by a Poincaré disk. A diffusion processes in $u=|z$, $z \in [0,1]$ with time $\tau = \frac{l^2}{4\pi\mu} \frac{K'}{K} \in \mathbb{L}(\mu \text{ thermal conductivity})$ as a chaotic component measured as orbiting plus completed orbital time as a pseudo-periodic component.

Point addition on E_λ creates a quartic polynomial on \mathbb{X}_2 solvable and reducible to Weierstrass normal form. A hyperelliptic Riemann surface \mathbb{X}_2 of two layers $s=0,1$ with modular invariant differential $D_s = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial u_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_{0'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_{1'}} \right) \sigma(u)\sigma(u')|_{u' \rightarrow u}$

consists of four layers u_s with $s=0,1,0',1'$ [11]. The Hurwitz automorphism theorem $\sum_{i=1}^w 1 - r_i^{-1} = \chi(\mathbb{X}_0) = 2$ [12] prescribes four layers as a tiling of the torus with four branch points $r_i=\{2,2,2,2\}$ or three branch points $r_i=\{2,3,6\}$, $\{2,4,4\}$ or $\{3,3,3\}$. Here $\chi(E)$ is the Euler-Poincaré characteristic of a line bundle of genus d [13] [14]. The branched covering can be visualized as a tiling of the Euclidean plane by triangles with angles π/r_1 , π/r_2 and π/r_3 as hexagonal or quadratic lattices. The number of $\delta\mathbb{X}$ branch points w is identical to the number of generators $(\alpha, \beta) = 1^{\frac{1}{r_i}}$ as rational self-maps $L = \alpha u + \beta$ of the torus to itself (Lattes map).

$\delta\mathbb{X}$ consists of a direct sum of lattices $M_d\mathbb{L}_d$ in $\{\mathbb{X}_1(1)\cup\mathbb{X}_2\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_1(1)\cup\mathbb{X}_2\cup\mathbb{X}_2\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_1(1)\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_0)\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_1)\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_0')\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_1')\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_2\cup\mathbb{X}_2\}$, $\{\mathbb{X}_1(M_0)\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_1)\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_0')\cup\mathbb{X}_1(M_1')\}$. The Weber- Schottky problem \mathbb{X}_d for $d=3,4,5$ predicts $\binom{d-2}{2} = (0,1,3)$ independent Lagrange parameter [15].

3d-3 Fenchel- Nielsen coordinates are equivalent to rotation angles of d-1 spheres situated within a given sphere. An arbitrary sphere $\mathbb{S}^2\{x^2+\mathbf{x}_i \mathbf{a}_i=p_i\}$ is indexed by \mathbf{a}_i and p_i , the power of a point of origin with respect to the sphere at inversion.,

Maximal five independent spheres ($i=1,\dots,5$) $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ require $\det(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i, 1)=0$ leading to a determinant of fourth order [16] for index permutations $\pi(i,j)$

$$\det A[\delta a, \delta p] = \prod_{\substack{i \neq j \\ \pi(i,j)}} \det(a_i - a_j, p_i - p_j) = 0 \quad (0.5)$$

The dimension of $\delta\mathbb{X}$ is proportional to the number topological paths connecting disks S_d or spheres $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$.

The Kronecker- Weber- Hilbert theorem (KWHT) consists in generating cyclotomic fields and cyclic field extensions as a pseudo-cyclic component in λ . Then a number- theoretic transform (NTT) exists for congruences of quadruple iteration indices 2^{2^k} . The Feigenbaum constants δ_F and α_F are supposed to be transcendental. However a transcendental field $\mathbb{N}[j(\sqrt{\Delta})]$ exhibits a complexity by orders of magnitude higher than an algebraic cubic field $\mathbb{K}[\partial]$ [4]. A precise numerical calculation of δ_F and α_F exhibits a [17] strong dependent on the degree of transformation N. The present paper develops an algebraic and number- theoretic approach to δ_F and α_F based on cubic irrationalities, elliptic units [18] and number transforms (NT). Elliptic units and modular invariants are transcendental for number fields $\mathbb{N}[j(\sqrt{\Delta})]$ as well algebraic in $\mathbb{K}[f(\sqrt{\Delta})]$ with elliptic invariant j and Weber- Schlaefli invariant $f(\sqrt{d})$ [19].

For a period lattice change $-iK^2 d\omega = K \wedge dK'$. $K(\lambda)$ and $K'(\lambda)$ depend on a pair complex-conjugated units ε and $\bar{\varepsilon}$ of the normal field $\mathbb{N}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ via $K \rightarrow \varepsilon K$ where $\varepsilon \bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} f^3(\sqrt{\Delta})$. Then $u_k \simeq d\omega \simeq \delta f^3(\omega)$. A transformation of (0.1) is a conjugate to an equianharmonic (EQ) center of complex plane \mathbb{C} .

3. Hermite transformations

Hermite transformations [9] $F(t, x) = \frac{f'(t)}{t-x} - \frac{1}{n} f(t)$ of a polynomial

$$f(t) = \sum_{i=0, \dots, n} \binom{n}{i} a_i x^{n-i} = 0$$

express power integral bases (PIB) $1, x, \dots, x^{n-1}$ and $1, t, \dots, t^{n-1}$ rationally.

Linear substituting roots $\gamma_\varphi x_i$ of a quartic polynomial $g(x) = \square$ yields a cubic polynomial $f(z) = \square$. Root maps $(ze_1 e_2 e_3 e_0) \rightarrow (x x_i x_j x_k x_l)$ yield p.14 [7]

$$g(x) = \frac{m_i^2}{(x-x_l)^4} f(z) \quad (0.6)$$

with $x_i = \varphi(u_i)$ and $f(x_i) = m_l = (lj)(lk)(li) \forall i, j, k, l = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ where the Hermite transformation γ_φ corresponds to the Weierstrass form

$$z - e_i = \gamma_\varphi(t) \circ z \quad (0.7)$$

$$\gamma_\varphi(t) = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{3} f'(t) & f(t) - \frac{t}{3} f'(t) \\ -1 & t \end{vmatrix}. \quad (0.8)$$

valid $\forall \gamma_\varphi(t)$ with $\gamma_\varphi \in \text{SL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$ [9].

The alternate expression

$$z - e \leftarrow F(t, z) = \frac{f(t)}{t-z} - \frac{1}{3} f'(t) \quad (0.9)$$

is a rational polynomial map expressing symbolically a PIB $t^i \rightarrow t_i$ [9] as a vector.

$\gamma_\varphi(t)$ are inequivalent transformations leading to CM.

For $n=3$ and $\sum e_i=0$ $F(t, z)$ yields

$$z \leftarrow F(t, z) = t_0 F_1 + t_1 F_0 \text{ where } (F_0, F_1) = (a_0 z + a_1, a_0 z^2 + a_1 z + 2a_2).$$

Introducing t -dependent coefficients

$$a(t), b(t) \text{ and } c(t), a(t) = t_0 a_0, b(t) = t_0 a_1 + t_1 a_0, c(t) = 2t_0 a_2 + t_1 a_1$$

$\gamma_\varphi(t) \circ z$ are subsequent iterations z_k of a quadratic map

$$z_{k+1} \leftarrow F(t, z_k) = a(t) z_k^2 + b(t) z_k + c(t) \quad (0.10)$$

with peculiarity

- (1) if $f(z_{k+1}) = 0$ then $\deg z_{k+1} = 3$
- (2) if $f(z_{k+1}) \neq 0$ $\deg z_{k+1} = 2^k$.

or in terms of elliptic units $g(u, \mathbb{L})$

- (1) if $z_{k+1}/z_k = g(u, \mathbb{L})$ then $\deg z_{k+1} = 3$
- (2) if $z_{k+1}/z_k \neq g(u, \mathbb{L})$ then $\deg z_{k+1} = 2^k$

Then period doubling is equivalent to multiplication of z by an elliptic unit $g(a\omega, \mathbb{L})$.

The PIB t_0, t_1, t_2 of polynomial $F(t, z)$ implies w. l. o. g. $\sum e_i = 0$. Then γ_φ are conjugate to linear, quadratic and cubic maps.

$\forall a_3$ a Mandelbrot map M_c

$$x_{k+1} \leftarrow x_k^2 + c$$

results from (0.10) by substituting with lemniscate (LE) parameter $a_0=1, a_1=t_1=0, 2a_2=c, t_0=1$ for harmonic parameter $\lambda=-1$

$$x_{k+1} \leftarrow \frac{x_{k+1}}{a}, x_k \leftarrow x_k + \frac{b}{2a} \text{ and } c \leftarrow -\frac{\Delta(t)}{4a^2(t)} \text{ where } \Delta(t) \leftarrow b^2(t) - 4a(t)c(t)$$

$\forall a_3$ a logistic map L_{t_0}

$$x_{k+1} \leftarrow t_0 x_k (1 - x_k)$$

results from (0.10) for EQ parameter $a_0=-1, a_1=a_2=0$ on a line $t_1=-t_0$ for $\lambda=1^{1/3}$.

M_c and T_{t_0} are conjugate maps

$$x_k \leftarrow t_0 \left(\frac{1}{2} - x_k \right) \text{ and } c = \frac{t_0}{2} \left(1 - \frac{t_0}{2} \right)$$

as EQ and LE limits of E_λ for a finite region t_0, t_1 on complex plane with axes t_0 and t_1 where a Hessian polynomial $H(t_0, t_1) \simeq \gamma_2$ vanishes quadratically.

Summarizing, conjugate quadratic maps M_c and L_t are conjugate to LE and EQ Hermite substitutions ($\lambda = -1$ and $1^{1/3}$) A Hermite- transform- solution of cubic roots is equivalent to Cardano 's method [9].

A second implication is that $\gamma_\wp(t)$ is isomorph to a nontrivial endomorphism of an elliptic curve E_λ over a subfield $\mathbb{K}(\partial)$ with Legendre modul λ

$\text{End}(E_\lambda/\mathbb{K}) \cong \{M \in \mathbb{C} : M\mathbb{L} \subset \mathbb{L}\} \neq \mathbb{Z}$. The Hermite transformation γ_\wp [9] has matrix elements as cubic or quadratic polynomials where $\det \gamma_\wp = f(t)$. If matrix elements of γ_\wp are cubic residues i.e. $\left[\frac{\gamma_\wp}{p} \right]_3 = 1$ then $\gamma_\wp \in \text{SL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$

represents an equivalent substitution. Then $\text{End}(E_\lambda/\mathbb{K}) \cong \text{CM}$ generates Tschirnhaus resolvents of (0.1) $j(\mathbb{L}) \leftarrow j(\gamma_\wp(t) \circ \mathbb{L})$. For class number one $h_\Delta=1$ $M \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$, $j(\mathbb{L}) \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ the invariant $j(\mathbb{L})$ are linear $\in \mathbb{N}$. A linear j -resolvent minimizes the $f(\omega)$ degree to 72 which reduces to 3 for $h_\Delta=1$. A $[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ yields a quartic polynomial (see Appendix 1). Transforming four roots to three on $s=1, \dots, \binom{4}{3}$ layers the projection map from \mathbb{L} to sphere \mathbb{S}^2 is up to a choice of normalization or calibration known as the Weierstrass \wp -function.

For fractional substitution $\gamma[e_i]$ of second order in $e_i = \wp(\omega_i)$ one has

$$\wp(u, \omega) = \gamma[e_i] \vartheta_{\left[\frac{g}{h} \right]}^2(u, \omega) \tag{0.11}$$

For Jacobi functions $\text{sn}^2(u, \sqrt{\lambda})$ or elliptic functions $s(u)$ for quartic roots $(0,1,l,m) \rightarrow (e_i) = 1/3 (2-l-m, 2l-m-1, 2m-l-1)$ [3] [20] one has

$$s^2(u) = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -\frac{1}{3}(e_2 - e_3) \\ 1 & \frac{1}{3}(e_3 - e_2) - (e_3 - e_1)(e_1 - e_2) \end{pmatrix} \wp(u)$$

and

$$s^2(u) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 + e_3 - e_1 & e_1 - e_3 \end{pmatrix} sn^2 \left(\sqrt{e_1 - e_3} u, \sqrt{\frac{e_2 - e_3}{e_1 - e_3}} \right).$$

4. Modular Units

Elliptic units [18] [21] are modular congruences in λ as modular units $g(a\omega, \mathbb{L})$

being modular-invariant Weierstrass sigma functions

$$g(a\omega, \mathbb{L}) = \Delta^{1/12} e^{-a\eta \cdot a\omega} \sigma(a\omega, \mathbb{L}) = \Delta^{1/12} e^{-\int_0^{a\omega} dv \zeta(v, M\mathbb{L})} \quad (0.12)$$

with $a = (r, s) \in \mathbb{Q}^2$, $\eta = \zeta(\omega/2, M\mathbb{L})$, $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2)$, $a\omega = r\omega_1 + s\omega_2$,

$$\tilde{\zeta}(v) = \zeta(v) - \omega\eta - \frac{1}{v}.$$

Klein forms $g(a\omega, \mathbb{L})$ differ from Siegel functions by the square of the Dedekind eta function $\eta^2(\omega)$ which is modular [2], e.g.

$$\eta^2(\omega) = \frac{(\frac{1}{2}0)(\frac{1}{2}0)(\frac{1}{2}0)}{(\frac{1}{3}0)(0\frac{1}{3})(\frac{1}{3}\frac{1}{3})(\frac{1}{3}-\frac{1}{3})} \quad (0.13)$$

where (a) denotes $g(a\omega, \mathbb{L})$. The Klein form g^{2N} is invariant under $\Gamma(N)$, leading to an infinity of $\eta^2(\omega)$ representations in terms of $\Gamma(N)$ and $\Gamma(N+1)$, e.g. [22].

(0.12) takes the form $g(a\omega) = \Delta^{1/12} \tilde{U}(a)$ with a mean value \tilde{a} in

$$\tilde{U}(a) = e^{-\tilde{a}\omega\tilde{\zeta}(a\omega)}.$$

A determination of r and s in a requires values of the differential operator $\frac{\partial}{\partial u}$ on

$\delta\mathbb{X}$ as an undecidable Diophantine problem. Elliptic and cyclotomic units are

norm-coherent numbers [23] [10] defined via norms in an extension field. For

cyclotomic units $e_N(1)$ the ratio of the number $e_N(u) = \left(1 - 1^{\frac{u}{N}}\right)$ is given by

$$\frac{e_N(u)}{e_{N+1}(u)} = \sum_{k=0, \dots, p-1} 1^{\frac{uk}{N+1}}$$

in terms of powers p^N generators for a of a prime p. The norm ratio for a

congruence number $p \approx 1 + \frac{u}{N}$

$$\frac{e_N(u)}{e_{N+1}(u)} \cong \frac{\left(1 + \frac{u}{N}\right)^{\binom{N-1}{2}}}{\left(1 + \frac{u}{N}\right)^{\binom{N}{2}}} = \left(1 + \frac{u}{N}\right)^{-N} \cong e^{-u} \text{ tends to an } N\text{-independent value for}$$

$N \rightarrow \infty$.

Using $\wp_u - \wp_v = \frac{\sigma_{u+v}\sigma_{u-v}}{\sigma_u^2\sigma_v^2}$ the $e_N(u)$ analogue is

$$E_N^{(e)}(u) = \frac{g(u_N + u_N^{(e)})g(u_N - u_N^{(e)})}{g^2(u_N^{(e)})} \quad (0.14)$$

where $u_N^{(e)} = 1^{e/e_\Delta} a \gamma_N \omega$, $u_N = a \omega$, $\gamma_N \in \Gamma(N)$ [10, 24]. In terms of the

normalized \wp - function $P(u) = \left(\varepsilon \frac{\wp(u)}{\sqrt{\Delta(\mathbb{L})}} \right)^{e_\Delta}$ one has with $\varepsilon^6 \in \mathbb{K}[\partial]$

$$P(u_N) - P(\gamma_N \omega) = \prod_{e=0}^{e_\Delta-1} (-\varepsilon) \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u)}{g^2(u_N)} \simeq \theta$$

generating a PIB $1, \theta, \theta^2, \dots, \theta^n$. Products over quadratic and hexagonal lattices with $e_\Delta=2$ and 3 yield $P \simeq \wp^2$ and $P \simeq \wp^3$. Regarding $\wp(u_N^{(e)})$ and $\wp(u_{N+1}^{(e)})$ as roots of a CM curve E_{λ_N} with

$$\lambda_N = \prod_{e=0,1,2; N \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)})}{\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_{N+1}^{(e)})} \simeq \prod_{e=0,1,2; N \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u) g^2(u_{N+1})}{E_{N+1}^{(e)}(u) g^2(u_N)}$$

5. Addition theorem for u , $\zeta(u)$ and $\wp(u)$ on δX

The matrix $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ is a quantum of the addition theorem on E_λ (see Appendix) for non-equidistant iterations k .

N -fold addition steps yield a determinant of order 2^{2^N} being an elliptic function [25] of order 2^{2^N} . First cycles are discussed enabling a fast composite

2^{2^N} algorithm for outer points k of $A_k = \{ u_k, \zeta_k \text{ or } \wp_k \}$ quadruple recursion

$$A_k = M(\mathbf{a}) A_k = A_{k-1} + a_{1k} A_{k-2} + a_{2k} A_{k-3} + a_{3k} A_{k-4} \quad (0.15)$$

exposed by quaternary unimodular collineations (0.51).

For definite a QCF reduce to, e.g. $a_i=0$ to BCF or $a_i=a_j=0$ to CF

Abelian cycles allow to replace the column $1,1,1,1$ in $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ by scaling parameter M_0, M_1, M_2, M_3 of CM for $\omega \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$.

Quadruple recursion steps are steps of the special Euclidean group $SE(3)$ for universal covering $u_k = \{ u_{k-1}, u_{k-2}, u_{k-3}, u_{k-4} \}$, Weierstrass zeta function

$\zeta_k = \{ \zeta_{k-1}, \zeta_{k-2}, \zeta_{k-3}, \zeta_{k-4} \}$ and Weierstrass \wp - function $\wp_k = \{ \wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}, \wp_{k-4} \}$. As a result the Poncelet theorem in space should have minimal four u -components [26].

The addition theorem of elliptic functions is given an invariant quartic polynomial (see Appendix).

Whereas a ternary algorithm (e. g. Jacobi- Perron) [27] [28] yields non- unique periodic sequences of Hermite's ∂ -problem four- components contain periodic CF, abelian number fields and invariants λ . Pseudo- random point addition on E_λ

is accompanied by pseudo-periodic orbits due to combinatorial. Inner points are invariant for unimodular collineations by

Theorem 1: $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ contain a tower $g(u) \rightarrow e^{g(u)}$ of modular units and Legendre modules $\lambda \rightarrow e^\lambda$ in the N- point limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ with a finite statistical probability.

Proof: The recursion string of $A_k \{A_{k-1}, A_{k-2}, A_{k-3}, A_{k-4}\}$ of $A = \{u, \zeta, \wp\}$ suffers collineations

$$A_k = A_{k-1} + a_{1k} A_{k-2} + a_{2k} A_{k-3} + a_{3k} A_{k-4} = M(\mathbf{a}) \{A_{k-1}, A_{k-2}, A_{k-3}, A_{k-4}\}.$$

For a particular collineation $a_1 = -2, a_2 = 1$

$$M(\vec{a}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

one gets

$$A_k = (A_{k-1} - A_{k-2}) - (A_{k-2} - A_{k-3}) + a_3 A_{k-4}.$$

$\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}$ result from a root transformation γ_\wp of a certain renormalized quartic equation. γ_\wp provides period doubling by modular units in $\mathbb{K}[\hat{\wp}]$. Then

$$A_k = (\lambda - 1)(A_{k-2} - A_{k-3}) + a_3 A_{k-4}.$$

Invariant (0.42) reflect collineations of point quadruples

$$u_k \leftarrow M(\vec{a}) \{u_{k-1}, u_{k-2}, u_{k-3}, u_{k-4}\}$$

$$\zeta_k \leftarrow M(\vec{a}) \{\zeta_{k-1}, \zeta_{k-2}, \zeta_{k-3}, \zeta_{k-4}\}$$

$$\wp_k \leftarrow M(\vec{a}) \{\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}, \wp_{k-4}\}$$

A triple $\{\wp_{k-1}, \wp_{k-2}, \wp_{k-3}\}$ as roots of invariant equation (0.42) constitute a

Legendre module λ and a pencil $\{E_\lambda\}$ for various k and corresponding $\{u_{k-1}, u_{k-2}, u_{k-3}\}, \{\zeta_{k-1}, \zeta_{k-2}, \zeta_{k-3}\}$.

Then invariants $(\lambda - 1)g^2(u)$ appear because e. g. $\delta_{\wp = \wp_{k-1} - \wp_{k-2}} = \gamma g^2(u)$ and

$$M(\mathbf{a}) \rightarrow (\lambda - 1)g^2(u) \oplus \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (0.16)$$

For a periodic CF of $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ an abelian field $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ is created as a CM

layer with $M_i \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$. Inverse collineations $M^{-1}(\vec{a})$ are unique for a principal ideal domain $h_\Delta = 1$ where Δ enters e_Δ [29]. It is claimed that the Hermite problem of expressing cubic irrationalities in terms of periodic sequences [28] of a ternary continued fraction algorithm can be treated as a CCF which split into invariants and CF as quadratic fields.

For $k \rightarrow \infty$ Legendre module λ and Feigenbaum constant δ_F get equivalent.

A_k are four points of an EQ invariant equation (0.42) within t-parameter space. EQ correspond to u_k - values

$$\frac{1}{3}\{(1,0),(1,1), (1,0),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{1}{3}\{(1,0),(1,-2), (1,2),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2) \text{ or}$$

$$\frac{1}{3}\{(1,1),(1,-1),(1,0),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{1}{3}\{(1,1),(1,2),(1,0),(0,1)\}(\omega_1, \omega_2)$$

leading to $\mathbf{a} = \frac{1}{3}(\bar{\mp}1, \bar{\mp}2)(\omega_1, \omega_2)$ in terms of half- periods ω_1 and ω_2 [30]. The cross ratio $\lambda = 1^{\frac{1}{3}}$ depends on 8 nontrivial combinations of ω_1 and ω_2 fractions for four parameters u_s .

If $a_{i+1} = T_3(a_i)$ the series $\{A_k\}$ yield a Cantor string zeta function $\zeta_{CS}(k)$ [31].

Here T_3 is the tent map on $I_0 = [0, \frac{1}{2}]$ and $I_1 = [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ [32] where

$$T_c(u) = (-1)^{\text{int}(cu)}(cu) \text{ mod } 1 \quad (0.17)$$

and $T_c^{\circ k}(u) = T_c^k(u)$ for k^{th} map $\circ k$.

CF and λ imply congruence modules 2^{2^k} in $\zeta_{CS}(k)$

$$\zeta_{CS}(k) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} 2^n 3^{-(n+1)k} \quad (0.18)$$

reflecting that a pole at complex k_{CS} is equivalent to

$$\sum_{N \text{ mod } (2^{2^k} - 1)} \zeta_{CS}(N) = \oint dz \zeta_{CS}(z) = 2H_{CS} \oint \frac{dza(z+z_0)}{e^z - 1} = 2H_{CS} a(z_0).$$

6. Diffeomorphisms of the interval $I = [0, 1]$ into itself

N point addition on E_λ corresponds to nonlinear dynamical systems with hyperelliptic measure $\mu(dx)$ for a quartic polynomial (0.42) [3]

$$\mu_h(dx) = \frac{dx}{2K\sqrt{\Phi(x)}} \quad (0.19)$$

in comparison to a measure for the logistic map L_c

$$\mu_l(dx) = \frac{dx}{\pi\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (0.20)$$

A hyperelliptic measure (0.19) with $\deg \Phi(x) = 4$ is directly related to Jacobi theta functions $\vartheta(u, \mathbb{L})$ for quarter periods K and K' .

Lebesgue measures μ_h and μ_l differ by the ratio K/π which can be determined via an arithmetic-geometric (agM) algorithm in terms of theta constants $\vartheta(2^k \mathbb{L})$ for $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Jacobi inversion for an elliptic function $x(u)$ allows to define implicitly a diffeomorphisms $\chi(x)$ of unit interval $I = [0, 1]$ into itself given

$$\chi(x) = \frac{1}{K} x^{-1}(\sqrt{x}) = \int_0^x \mu_h(dx) \simeq \int \frac{du}{K} + \lambda_3 \chi(E) \quad (0.21)$$

on $0 \leq x \leq 1$ as exactly solvable chaos [3] where $\chi(x) = \sin^{-1}(x)$ for (0.20)

containing a Lagrange multiplier λ_3 and the Euler- Poincaré characteristic $\chi(E)$:

In case of K-congruences $\chi(x)$, u , ζ , \wp evolve in d- dimensional $\delta\mathbb{X}$ which can be regarded by an alternating d-form E of a line bundle of type $diag(d_i)$. The condition that $\delta\mathbb{X}$ is reducible to a torus $M_d\mathbb{L}$ is given by a vanishing Euler-Poincaré characteristic [33]

$$\chi(E) = \frac{1}{d!} \int_{\delta\mathbb{X}} \wedge^d c_1(E) = (-1)^d \prod_{i=1, \dots, d} d_i du_i \wedge d\bar{u}_i \quad (0.22)$$

with first Chern class

$$c_1(E) = \sum_{i=1}^d c_i du_i \wedge d\bar{u}_i.$$

7. Legendre module λ and Feigenbaum constant on $\delta\mathbb{X}$

The Legendre module $\lambda = \frac{e_{0k} - e_{0k+1}}{e_{0k+1} - e_{0k+2}}$ is equivalent to the Feigenbaum constant

$$\delta_F = \frac{c_k - c_{k+1}}{c_{k+1} - c_{k+2}} \text{ if period doubling parameter } c_k \text{ and roots } e_{0k} \text{ of (0.42) are}$$

equivalent on $\{E_{\lambda_N}\}$ on $\delta\mathbb{X}$.

$f(\omega)$ and λ experience fluctuations based on

- (1) pseudo-random point- addition on elliptic curves E_λ
- (2) γ_\wp roots shift on universal covering $\delta\mathbb{X}$.
- (3) λ - dependent exponent of λ

The algebraic unit $\frac{f(\omega)}{2^{1/3}}$ for $-\Delta=3 \pmod{8}$ or equation (0.1) for Weber- Schlaefli invariant $f(\sqrt{\Delta})$ can be transformed by an infinite number of inequivalent quadratic Hermite substitutions γ_\wp . Each substitution denotes a quadratic transformation within e.g. the well-known field $\mathbb{K}[2^{1/3}]$. The eighth power $x=f^8(\omega)$ satisfies $x^3 - \gamma_2 x - 2^4 = 0$ with Weber invariant $\gamma_2 = \frac{f^{24}(\omega) - 2^4}{f^8(\omega)}$. $f(\omega)$ fluctuations due to (0.7) transmit to x- and χ -fluctuations as

$$\delta\chi = \delta f \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\Phi(x)}} \simeq (\delta x + \dots + \delta x^4) \simeq \delta f^8(\omega) + \dots + \delta f^{32}(\omega)$$

A transform $r_N(x)$ of degree N [30]

$$x_{k+1} = r_N(x_k) \quad (0.23)$$

transforms (0.1) into an infinite set $E, F \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$. Cubic residues i.e. $\left[\frac{\gamma_\wp}{p}\right]_3 = 1$ in

$\gamma_\wp \in \text{SL}(2, \mathbb{Z})$ and $E, F \in \mathbb{Q}$ for $h_\Delta=1$ induce chaotic tessellations of the hyperbolic plane \mathbb{H} where a flow of the bifurcation diagram is stable for a diffusive time

$$\tau = \frac{l^2}{4\pi\mu} \frac{K'}{K} \in \text{ML}.$$

Coefficients c_k in δ_F correspond to roots $e_k \in \mathbb{K}(\partial)$. Period-doubling at $k \rightarrow k+1, k+2$ are addition steps $\gamma_\phi X_k \rightarrow X_{k+1}$, $\gamma_\phi X_{k+1} \rightarrow X_{k+2}$, $\gamma_\phi C_k \rightarrow C_{k+1}$, $\gamma_\phi C_{k+1} \rightarrow C_{k+2}$ as invariances of (0.42).

Theorem 2. In the N point limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ the Legendre module $\lambda_N(\delta_\phi)$ tends to the Feigenbaum constant $\delta_F \cong 4,669\dots$ on universal covering $\delta\mathbb{X}$ for pencils of elliptic curves $\{E_{\lambda_N}\}$ caused by period-doubling as a quadratic transformation $\{a\} = \frac{1}{2}\{(1,0),(0,1),(1,1)\}$ of $\sigma(u)$.

Proof: E_λ point addition can be scaled to EQ invariant $A_1^3 = A_2^3$ because u , ζ and ϕ suffer homogeneity transformations M_d, M_d^{-1}, M_d^{-2} .

In case of $\sigma_3 = \frac{1}{4}$ one gets a hexagonal lattice $M_d\mathbb{L}$ with the omega-2 constant

$$\omega_e = \frac{\Gamma^3\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)}{4\pi} \cong 1.5299 \quad (0.24)$$

$A_1^3 = A_2^3$ gives for modular units

$$g^4(10) + g^4(01) + g^4(11) = 0$$

$$\text{and } \lambda_{N=2} = -\frac{g^4(10)}{g^4(01)} \quad (0.25)$$

where $\{a\} = \frac{1}{2}\{(1,0),(0,1),(1,1)\}$ corresponds to period-doubling.

A modular unit with rational $a=(r, s) \in \mathbb{Q}^2$ is a ϑ -translate

$$g(a\omega) \simeq 1^{r^2\omega_1+rs\omega_2}\vartheta_1((r\omega_1+s\omega_2)\pi, \omega) \quad (0.26)$$

of the Jacobi theta function ϑ_1 . Then $\eta^{2N}(\omega)$ is a product of modular units $g(a\omega)$ in $\Gamma(N)$ [21] [18].

Rational \mathbf{a} result from Diophantine equations including cubic residues i. e.

$$\left[\frac{\gamma_\phi}{p}\right]_3 = 1 \pmod{p}. \text{ The indices } k \text{ or } s=0, 0', 1, 1' \text{ denote hyperelliptic layer on } \delta\mathbb{X}.$$

Pseudo-random values A_{q_s} are eigenvalues $D_s \sigma(u)\sigma(u') = \tilde{\zeta}(a\omega)\sigma(u)\sigma(u')$

of the differential operator $D_0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial u_0} - \frac{\partial}{\partial u_{0'}}$, $D_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial u_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial u_{1'}}$ on $\delta\mathbb{X}$ -tori and

reducible hyperelliptic $\sigma(u)\sigma(u')$.

Diophantine values $\{a\}$ are viewed as Hilbert's tenth problem which is not decidable. Tessellations of \mathbb{H} are influenced by chaotic lines. The situation can be characterized by a bifurcating potential flow which is stable against small periodic motions of particles.

It is expected that $e_i \simeq 1^{2r^2\omega_1+2rs\omega_2}$ giving $e_i^{qk} = c_{0i} + c_{1i}e^{kc_{2i}}$ for (q_{10}, q_{01}, q_{11}) with $c_2 = \omega_e$. Experimentally one has $c_2 = 1.530$ [32] $\simeq \omega_e$ which yields a rough

estimation for the period doubling expression (0.25) $\lambda_{N=2} = e^{w_e} \cong e^{1.5299} \cong 4.617$.

Further refinement is expected via statistics in Section 9.

8. A relation $\delta_F \alpha_F^2$ on $\delta \mathbb{X}$

Corollary 2: The quotient $\prod_{e,N} \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u)g^2(u_{N+1})}{E_{N+1}^{(e)}(u)g^2(u_N)}$ for $N \rightarrow \infty$ tends to a constant term

$\lambda_N(\delta \wp)g^2 \simeq \delta_F \alpha_F^2$ if $g^2 = \frac{\prod_C g^2(u_{N+1})}{\prod_{C'} g^2(u_N)}$ is a generator.

Proof: A zeta function of a normal field $\zeta(z, \mathbb{N}[j(\sqrt{\Delta})])$ transforms into a zeta function of a cyclotomic field [34] [35] [36] by replacing $\eta(z)$ by 1^z . Class number $h_{\Delta=1}$ differ from $h_N \rightarrow \infty$. $E_N(u)$ is the KWHT analogue of an abelian number

$e_N(u)$ as a norm coherent set. Periodic cycle maps $\gamma_{\wp} \circ \dots \circ \gamma_{\wp} = 1$ generalize

generators as roots of unity $g^2 = \frac{\prod_C g^2(u_{N+1})}{\prod_{C'} g^2(u_N)}$ where

$$\prod_{e,N} \frac{E_N^{(e)}(u)}{E_{N+1}^{(e)}(u)} = \prod_{e,N} \frac{g^2(u_N) \left(\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)}) \right)}{g^2(u_{N+1}) \left(\wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)}) \right)} = g^2 \lambda_N \quad (0.27)$$

assuming that $\wp(u_N)$ with $u_N = a\omega$ is a transformed quartic root.

Then $\lambda_N = \lambda_N(\delta \wp^{\circ k})$ for k^{th} maps $\delta \wp^{\circ k} = \wp(u_N) - \wp(u_N^{(e)}) = \gamma_{\wp}^{\circ k} \wp = \gamma_{\wp} \circ \dots \circ \gamma_{\wp} \wp$ and $\lambda_N = \lambda_N(\delta \wp^{\circ k}) = k \lambda_N(\delta \wp) = g^2 \lambda_N(\delta \wp)$. (see Theorem 3)

Corollary 3: Chaotic plaquettes

$$U_{\square} = \prod_{i=1, \dots, 4} U(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{a}_i) = 1 \quad (0.28)$$

with $U(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{a}_i) = e^{S(\mathbf{a}_i)} \tilde{U}(\mathbf{q}_i)$ (0.28) create an identity map for the simplest cycle with a finite statistical weight where $U_{\square} \simeq A_{\square}$.

Proof: A simplest cycle [37] consists of four points at $k, k+1, k+2, k+3$ where

$$z_k = z_{k+3} \text{ OR } z_{k+1} < z_k < z_{k+2} \text{ OR } z_{k+2} < z_k < z_{k+1}$$

for an interval $I(z, z')$ where $z_k = \wp(u_k)$. In terms of differences $\frac{E_N(u)}{g^2(u_N)} = z_{k+1} -$

$z_k < z_{k+2} - z_k = \frac{E_{N+1}(u)}{g^2(u_{N+1})}$ it depends on modular units $g(u)$. A bifurcation

diagram consists of lines as segments of $\{E_{\lambda}\}$ for interval $I_{k,k'}$. The simplest cycle is equivalent that three points z_k, z_{k+1}, z_{k+2} are on different sites of inflection lines of $\{E_{\lambda}\}$ and implies an inflection point. The inflection point condition is given by the l. h. s of (0.45) [38]. Four points collineated by matrix $M(\mathbf{a})$ depend on the

matrix exponential $e^{S(\mathbf{a})}$. Then $\exists \gamma_{\wp}(k, k+1)$ with $z_{k+1} = \gamma_{\wp}(k, k+1) z_k$ by identifying addition as root transforming. Then $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] \simeq A_{\square}(u_k) M(\mathbf{a})$

in (0.46) contains modular units $g(u) \frac{\prod_c g(u_c)}{\prod_{c'} g(u_{c'})}$ (see Appendix 2-4). Each

$A_k \leftarrow A e^{S(\mathbf{a})} \leftarrow A M(\mathbf{a}_k)$ results from a definite collineation $M(\mathbf{a}_k)$ of u, ζ, \wp acting on indices $k-1$ to $k-4$. Next we suppose that the collineation can be incorporated by a linear transformation of fourth order by

$$\sigma(u_k) \leftarrow \sigma(u_{k'}) M_{kk'}(\mathbf{a}) \leftarrow \exp\left(\int dv \zeta(v) + S(\mathbf{a})\right)$$

leading to non-commutative modular units:

$$A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] \simeq \frac{\prod_c g(u_c) M(\mathbf{a})}{\prod_{c'} g(u_{c'}) M(\mathbf{a}')} = \frac{\prod_i \tilde{U}(\mathbf{q}_i) e^{S(\mathbf{a}_i)}}{\prod_i \tilde{U}(\mathbf{q}'_i) e^{S(\mathbf{a}'_i)}} = \frac{\prod_i U(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{a}_i)}{\prod_i U(\mathbf{q}'_i, \mathbf{a}'_i)} \quad (0.29)$$

with matrix exponential $U(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{a}_i) = e^{S(\mathbf{a}_i)} \tilde{U}(\mathbf{q}_i)$

as a non-commutating 4×4 matrix. Sharkovskii's theorem predicts an infinite number of simplest cycles. Then modular units $g(u_N) \simeq g(\mathbf{a}\omega)$ of simplest cycles as a product of four $U(q_s)$ at $k, k+1, k+1, k+3$ yield the identity map (0.28)

Theorem 3: γ_{\wp} -dependent products $\lambda_N \Pi g^2$ on $\delta \mathbb{X}$ are equivalent to the differential topological entropy h_t and exhibit plateaus with zero self-intersection number.

$\lambda_N \Pi g^2$ for N -point addition/iteration in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ is equivalent to $\delta_F \alpha_F^2$.

Proof: $\delta \mathbb{X}$ with genera $d=1, \dots, 5$ is a d -dimensional complex generalized Riemann surface. The $\delta \mathbb{X}$ reduction to elliptic lattices yields a vanishing Euler-Poincaré characteristic and a vanishing self-intersection number. Feigenbaum constant δ_F and Legendre module λ are equivalent if iteration steps k are period-doublings, period-doublings are cubic roots as ramification of enveloping elliptic curves $\{E_\lambda\}$. $\{E_\lambda\}$ are stable against period motions in $\mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ and differ by elliptic units in $\mathbb{K}[\partial]$. For cubic roots $k, k+1$ and $k+2$ one has

$$\lambda_N(\delta \wp) \simeq 1 + \left\langle \frac{\wp_{k+1} - \wp_k - \wp_{k+2} + \wp_{k+1}}{\wp_{k+2} - \wp_{k+1}} \right\rangle \simeq 1 + \delta \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \ln \delta \wp \quad (0.30)$$

where δ denotes k -variation.

Here $\delta \wp_{k+1} = \delta \gamma_{\wp} \circ \wp_k$ and $\delta \wp_{k+N} = \delta \gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N} \circ \wp_k$

A supremum-algorithm yet to be determined relates the topological entropy

$$h_t(\gamma_{\wp}) = \sup_{d\mu(\gamma_{\wp})} h_{\mu}(\gamma_{\wp}) \text{ with Lyapunov exponents } \lambda_L(\gamma_{\wp})$$

$$h_{\mu}(\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N}) = \lambda_L(\gamma_{\wp}^{\circ N}) = 2^{-N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \ln \gamma'_{\wp}(\wp_i)$$

for $N=g^k$ and metrical entropy $h_{\mu}(\gamma_{\wp})$.

In view of (0.27) one has for a generator g^2 with $\wp_{k+1}=\gamma_\wp\circ\wp_k=\gamma_\wp\circ g^2(u)$ due to (0.11).

The difference $\delta\wp$ can be written as $\delta\gamma_\wp\circ\wp_k$ because

$$\begin{aligned} z - e_i &= \wp_{k+1} - \wp_{k+2} = \delta\gamma_\wp(t) \circ \wp_k, \\ (\wp_{k+1} - \wp_{k+2})^{-1} &= -\delta\gamma_\wp^{-1}(t) \circ (-\wp_k^{-1}) \\ \lambda_N(\gamma_\wp^{g^k}) &= 1 - \frac{\delta}{\delta k} \langle \lambda_L(\gamma_\wp) \rangle = 1 - \frac{\partial h_t(\gamma_\wp^{g^k})}{\partial k} \end{aligned} \quad (0.31)$$

Then $\delta\wp^{\circ N} = \gamma_\wp^{\circ N} \delta\wp$ and $h_t(\gamma_\wp^{\circ g^k}) = g^k h_t(\gamma_\wp)$ [39]

Alternatively $\delta\wp = \gamma_\wp g^2$ and $\lambda_N(\delta\gamma_\wp^{\circ N}) \simeq 1 + \delta \frac{1}{N} \sum \ln \delta g^2$.

Then the topological entropy h_t yields an one- dimensional optimization

$\delta g^2 = (g_k + g_{k+1})(g_k - g_{k+1})$ and $N = g_k^{g_{k+1}}$ where $g_k = g(u_k)$ which enters the deciphering algorithm of the fine structure constant in [40].

Corollary 4: $\lambda_N(\delta\wp)$ is equivalent to changes of topological entropy

$$\begin{aligned} ch_t(\gamma_\wp^{\circ N}) &\simeq NH_{CS}. \text{ EQ curves correspond to } \gamma_\wp^{\circ N} \text{ with } N=2^k \text{ and} \\ h_t(\gamma_\wp) &= H_{CS}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: In case of EQ γ_\wp is generated from an invariant $f(t)=t^3 \mp 1=0$ equivalent to $t^3 \pm 1 = \pm 2$ giving $\det(\gamma_\wp) = f(t) = \pm 2$.

Subsequent maps $\gamma_\wp^{\circ N}$ yield $N = \det(\gamma_\wp)^k = (-1)^k \cdot 2^k$. CM curves generalize a Landen transform (0.2) to complex $\lambda(\delta\gamma_\wp)$ as a composite algorithm having lowest complexity. A k -cycle with $k \rightarrow 2^k$ implies a congruence mod 2^k-1 which yields $N = 2^k$

Subsequent $k \rightarrow 2^k$ generate Fermat number F_k transforms. First four F_k are prime having generator b^{2^k} with $b=2$ or $b=3$ as roots of unity [5]. With

$$\lambda_N(\delta\wp^{\circ N}) \simeq \frac{\partial}{\partial k} h_t(k) \simeq N \ln 2 \simeq \tilde{N} \ln 3 \text{ one gets}$$

$$h_t(\gamma_\wp^{\circ b^N}) = b^N H_{CS} \text{ with } \lambda \rightarrow 1-\lambda \text{ symmetry in (0.31)}$$

The second Feigenbaum constant α_F determines k doubling as follows [41]

$$z^{\circ 2k} = -\alpha_F z^{\circ k} \quad (0.32)$$

In view of a NT α_F is equivalent to a cyclic shift of z_{k+1} for a generator g

$$z_{k+1} = g z_k \text{ and } z_{2k} = g^k z_k.$$

(0.32) is equivalent to renormalized equations $-\alpha_F g(g(-z/\alpha_F)) = g(z)$.

The existence of the second Feigenbaum constant α_F is equivalent to a number transform with generator $g(u)$. Equivalences of Legendre module $\lambda \rightarrow 1-\lambda$ transmit

to δ_F . Computed δ_F and α_F from [17] are summarized in Table in dependence on the transformation degree N of (0.23)

N	δ_F	α_F	$\delta_F \alpha_F^2$
2	4.67	2(2.5)	29.19
3	6.08	1.93	22,64
4	7.29	1.69	20,82
5	8.35	1.56	20,32
6	9.3	1.47	20,1
7	10.2	1.41	20,28
8	10.95	1.36	20,25
10	12.37	1.29	20,58

Tabelle Relation $\delta_F \alpha_F^2$ for transformation degrees = {2-8,10} from [17]

Thus, $(\delta\wp)g^2 \simeq \delta_F \alpha_F^2$ in terms of Legendre module $\lambda_N(\delta\wp)$, Feigenbaum constant δ_F , α_F and generator g^2 can be explained by changes of topological entropy.

N=2 values for M_t and T_c exhibit deviations which are explained by the non-uniqueness of $g(u)$ bases corresponding to either 2^1 powers of 2 or 2^1 powers of 3 both being roots of unity for the first four prime Fermat number

9. λ and δ_F statistics

The inflection point condition (0.45) can be generalized by a linear shift of $\zeta(u)$ as a σ - product

$$\begin{vmatrix} M_0 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ M_1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ M_2 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ M_3 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} = \frac{\prod_{C_d} \sigma(u_{C_d})}{\prod_{C'_d} \sigma(u_{C'_d})} = 0$$

depending on a N-fold direct sum in contour space C_d and C'_d generalizing $C(ijkl)$

in $\lambda = e^{\int_C(ijkl) dv\zeta(v)} = \frac{\prod_C \sigma(u_C)}{\prod_{C'} \sigma(u_{C'})} = \exp(\int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$ for a product $\lambda_N =$

$\prod_{ijkl}(ijkl)$ [1] [26] due to Poncelet closure [1]. Though independent on the path between segment endpoints a statistical dependence on N and on collineations $\Pi M(\mathbf{a})$ arises. Modular and cyclotomic units yield a path dependence on a complex k- contour $\lambda(\delta\wp) \simeq \exp(\sum_k \int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$.

With $N \ln f(\omega) \simeq H_{CS}^d$ a tower of modular units yields $1^{\frac{1}{N}}$ projects onto \mathbb{C}^d : In case of $N \rightarrow \infty$ the product of modular units yields a closed complex k- contour in the exponential map $\exp(\sum_k \int_{C-C'} dv\zeta(v))$ via Stokes theorem

$$\lambda(\delta\wp) \simeq \exp(\sum_k \int dv\zeta(v) + \lambda_{CS} \sum_k \int dv \wedge dv'(\wp(v) - \wp(v'))) \quad (0.33)$$

with CM in $d \leq 5$ disk segments $S_d [M_d \mathbb{L}]$ residues $\lambda_{CS} \approx H_{CS}$.

On genus d surfaces $S_d [M_d \mathbb{L}]$ Lagrange multiplier $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ for conditions (0.47) (0.28) and (0.22)

$$\lambda = \prod_i \exp \left(\int_{C_i} du \zeta(u) + \lambda_1 A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] + \lambda_2 (1 - U_{\square}) + \lambda_3 \chi \right) \quad (0.34)$$

via Lagrange multiplier for nilpotency $N^2 = \det A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] = 0$, for the existence of the simplest cycle and a zero self-intersection number $\chi(E)$ (0.22).

Collineations $u \rightarrow M(\vec{a})u$ changing $C(ijkl)$ into $C_M(ijkl)$ yield correlation

functions $\frac{\delta}{\delta C_M} \int_C dv \zeta$ which dominate λ .

On a disk S_d one has the exact equation [7]

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda} \lambda \lambda' \frac{dK_d}{d\lambda} = \lambda \lambda' \frac{d^2 K_d}{d\lambda^2} + (1 - 2\lambda) \frac{dK_d}{d\lambda} = \frac{K_d}{4} \quad (0.35)$$

giving solution (0.2). Our aim is to describe a linearized and invertible $K(\lambda)$ solution as a γ_{\wp} substitution of (0.1). This leads to a symmetry in $(\zeta\kappa)$ and (zk) descriptions of [6].

The following Ansatz considers a zero of $\lambda(\delta_{\wp})$ at $u \in M_d \mathbb{L}$ and a pole in

derivatives $\frac{d}{d\lambda_d} = \frac{i}{\sigma_s} \frac{d}{d\lambda_{d+1}} + \Lambda(u, M_{d+1} \mathbb{L})$ on $S_d [M_d \mathbb{L}]$. The Heuman Lambda

function $\Lambda(u, M_{d+1} \mathbb{L})$ tends to a constant if $K \rightarrow 0$. The surface tension σ_s reflect changes of topological entropy h_t between $S_d [M_d \mathbb{L}]$ and $S_{d+1} [M_{d+1} \mathbb{L}]$. Zeros of λ (0.35) are treated by an N-oscillator equation at $u \in M_{d+1} \mathbb{L}$

$$K_d^3 + K_d'' - \sigma_s^2 (1 - H^2 \lambda^2) K_d = 0 \quad (0.36)$$

and

$$(1 - 2\lambda) K_d' - \frac{1}{4} K_d = 0 \quad (0.37)$$

K_d'' inserted into (0.35) yields both cubic equations for $K(\lambda)$ as well for $\lambda(K)$

$$(1 - 2\lambda) K' + \sigma_s^2 \lambda \lambda' (1 - H^2 \lambda^2) K - \lambda \lambda' K^3 - \frac{1}{4} K = 0$$

Which can be expanded in terms of $f(\omega)$ satisfying the cubic polynomial (0.1).

Equation (0.36) splits into 1-oscillator solutions in form of Hermite polynomials

$$\frac{d^2 K}{d\lambda^2} - \lambda \frac{dK}{d\lambda} + nK = 0. \quad (0.38)$$

As a partial solution of (0.37) one has

$$K \simeq \frac{c}{(\lambda - \frac{1}{2})^{1/8}} \text{ and } K \simeq \sigma_s \sqrt{1 - H^2 \lambda^2}$$

A linear solution $K \simeq \lambda$ requires four-components of u, ζ, \wp . In this case a

Feigenbaum constant δ_F is equivalent to a quarter period K and induces a third

order phase transition. Simultaneously λ is an exponential map of a tower of modular units $g(u)$ as a solution of (0.35). Writing $g(u)$ in terms of idempotents λ can be linearized. Equations (0.34) and (0.36) induce a discussion of flux quantization [42] in quantum statistics in [43].

10. Conclusions

Both first Feigenbaum constant δ_F and Legendre module λ suffer complex fluctuations on universal covering $\delta\mathbb{X}$ and get equivalent.

Pseudo- random point addition on elliptic curves E_λ exhibits pseudo- cyclic variables. Pseudo- cyclic variables correspond to cycles and periods of one-dimensional maps as Hermite substitutions of a cubic polynomial. The quartic polynomial (0.42) is in agreement with the Feigenbaum renormalization functional $g(z)$ [44]. A Hermite substitution γ_ϕ is conjugate to M_c and to T_{t_0} as LE and EQ elliptic curves.

Iterating u^{*k} , u^{*k+1} and u^{*k+2} creates modular units λ_N of E_λ of a quartic polynomial (0.50).

This corresponds to a k -space $S_d \in \mathbb{C}^5$ of five independent nested disks $S_d \simeq$ spheres $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}, p)$ around k embedded in a \mathbb{L} . At computation disks S_d [$M_d L$] correspond to cardioids of Mandelbrot set. Modular units are cyclotomic units on S_d . A relation between Lorange multiplier λ_i corresponds to λ , $g(u)$, δ_F and α_F . The situation is equivalent to Planck units G , \hbar and c expressing physical fields with independent coupling constant G .

The second Feigenbaum constant α_F is equivalent to a generator $g(u)$ as a mean cyclic shift. The relation $\delta_F \alpha_F^2 = \text{constant}$ is valid if a generator $g(u)$ exists for arbitrary transformation degrees N in (0.23) A relation of Legendre module λ_N to modular units of modular groups $\Gamma(N)$ as Sharkovsky ordering of combinatorial dynamics [37] needs further discussion

Appendix 1

A relation between spheres $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ and collineations $M(\mathbf{a})$

Coordinates on a sphere $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ depend on four parameter u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 satisfying relations which remain valid on Riemann surfaces \mathbb{X}_g .

First Weierstrass relations of elliptic sigma functions $\sigma(u, \mathbb{L})$ with $x(u)+x(v)+x(w)=0$ and $x(u)=\sum \sigma(u_1) \sigma(u_2) \sigma(u_3)\sigma(u_4)$ are valid for $u, v, w \cong (1, S, S^2)u$ and remain valid on $\delta\mathbb{X}$ with Rosenhain relations [45]

$$2^g x[\eta](v) = \sum_{[\varepsilon]} (-1)^{\varepsilon \wedge \eta} x[\varepsilon](u) \text{ with}$$

$$x[\varepsilon](u) = (-1)^{(\rho+\sigma)\varepsilon'} \vartheta_{[\varepsilon]}(u_1) \vartheta_{[\varepsilon+\rho]}(u_2) \vartheta_{[\varepsilon+\sigma]}(u_3) \vartheta_{[\varepsilon-\rho-\sigma]}(u_4)$$

where $\vartheta_{[\varepsilon]}(u)$ denotes a hyperelliptic theta function with characteristics $[\varepsilon] \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon' \end{bmatrix} \in F_2^{2g}$. Four- component parameter u, v, w are related to spherical triangles.

A spherical triangle of arc length' a, b, c , angles α, β, γ yields four-component parameter u, v, w with $\tan(\frac{1}{2}m_0(2\pi, a, b, c))=ie^v$ and $\tan(\frac{1}{2}m_0(2\pi, \alpha, \beta, \gamma))=ie^w$ via matrices [46]

$$m_0 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & -1 \end{vmatrix} \text{ and } S_0 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

One has $(u, v, w)=(1, S, S^2)u$ as three four- component variables $\cong X, Y, Z$ on \mathbb{S}^2 .

Here $S = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)S_0$, $S^3=1$, $S_0^2 = 1$.

Right multiplication $u \leftarrow uM(\vec{a})$ of u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 by $M(\vec{a})$ changes contour $C(ijkl)$ and Legendre module via $C_M(ijkl) \leftarrow C(ijkl)$.

An uncertainty of spheres $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}_i, p_i)$ with respect to \mathbf{a}_i permutations in order to find a relation to $M(\vec{a})$ is enhanced by changes $u \rightarrow u + \frac{1}{2} \hat{U} \mathbb{L}$, $v \rightarrow v + \frac{1}{2} S \hat{U} \mathbb{L}$ and $w \rightarrow w + \frac{1}{2} S^2 \hat{U} \mathbb{L}$ via a shift with a 2×4 rectangular matrix $\hat{U}_i \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ mod } 2$. Thus $1, \dots, 2^8$ substitutions leave the addition theorem invariant. Summed up iterations u shifted by $\sum_{l=1}^{2^8} b_l S^r U \mathbb{L}$ giving in total a group $G_{2^{2^8}}$ of the order 2^{2^8} where $r=(1, 2, 3)$ and binary number b_l .

Appendix 2

Addition theorem of $\mathbf{x}_1= \mathbf{x}_k=p(u)$, $\mathbf{x}_2= \mathbf{x}_{k+1}=p(v)$ and $\mathbf{x}_3= \mathbf{x}_{k+2}=p(u \mp v)$

Three points on E_λ given by [30]

$$\wp'^2(u) = f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^3 \binom{3}{i} a_i x^{3-i} \quad (0.39)$$

yield

$$a_0(x_k+x_{k+1}+x_{k+2}) + 3a_1 = \left(\frac{\sqrt{f(x_k)} \pm \sqrt{f(x_{k+1})}}{x_k - x_{k+1}} \right)^2 \quad (0.40)$$

leading to a quadratic [30] equation

$$4[a_0\sigma_3+a_3][3a_0\sigma_1+3a_1] - [3a_0\sigma_2-3a_2]^2 = 0 \quad (0.41)$$

in terms of elementary symmetric polynomials

$$3\sigma_1=\sum x_i, 3\sigma_2=\sum x_i x_j \text{ and } \sigma_3 = x_1 x_2 x_3.$$

Points x_i ($i = 1,2,3 \rightarrow k, k+1, k+2$) in (0.41) are viewed as roots of a cubic polynomial

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^3 \binom{3}{i} \sigma_i(x_1, x_2, x_3) x^{3-i}$$

Introducing $\sigma_4 = 4\sigma_1\sigma_3 - 3\sigma_2^2$ and $\sigma_0=1$ for symbolic $\sigma_i \rightarrow \sum_1^{4-i} \sum_2^i$ and $a_i = A_1^{4-i} A_2^i$ equation (0.41) transforms into

$$\Phi(y) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \binom{4}{i} a_i \sigma_i = \sum_{i=0}^4 \binom{4}{i} A_1^{4-i} A_2^i \sum_1^{4-i} \sum_2^i = 0 \quad (0.42)$$

where a_4 automatically satisfies

$$a_0 a_4 - 4a_1 a_3 + 3a_2^2 = 0 \quad (0.43)$$

Subsequent points x_k, x_{k+1}, x_{k+2} on E_λ yield a simple invariant- theoretic formulation (0.42) which introduces, however, differential equations of high complexity as Diophantine equations.

If $u=v$ then $x_1=x_2=x=p(u)$ and $x_3=p(2u)$ one gets the doubling map on E_λ [25]

$$\wp(2u) = \frac{(\wp_u^2 + g_2/4)^2 + 2g_3\wp_u}{4\wp_u^3 - g_2\wp_u - g_3} \quad (0.44)$$

An expression $\wp(2u)$ in terms of $\wp(u)$ is rational if invariants if $g_2, g_3 \in \mathbb{Z}$:

$$W_1(z) = \frac{(z^2+1)^2}{4(z^3-z)} (g_2=4, g_3=0) \text{ and } W_2(z) = \frac{z(z^3+8)}{z^3-1} (g_2=0, g_3=4) \text{ which are intensively}$$

investigated.

Taylor expansions of $\det \zeta(u_i+u_j)$ on a finite difference grid $(\Delta u)^i \frac{\partial^i}{\partial u^i}$ of $\ln \sigma(u)$

where $\prod_{u_i=u+ih, 0 < i < j \leq N} \Pi(u_i - u_j) \neq 0$ yield an elliptic function of Nth order

$$\frac{\prod_c \sigma(u_c)}{\prod_{c'} \sigma(u_{c'})} [38] [47] \text{ as matrix of derivatives } \wp_j^{(i)}.$$

\wp satisfies a cubic invariant equation on S_d as a Tschirnhaus resolvent.

Then $x_1(u), x_2(v)$ and $x_3(u \mp v)$ result from Hermite substitutions of roots of a quartic invariant equation [30].

One has

$$\begin{vmatrix} \zeta'_{02} - \zeta'_{01} & \zeta'_{03} - \zeta'_{01} \\ \zeta''_{02} - \zeta''_{01} & \zeta''_{03} - \zeta''_{01} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & \zeta'_{01} & \wp'_{01} \\ 1 & \zeta'_{02} & \wp'_{02} \\ 1 & \zeta'_{03} & \wp'_{03} \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (0.45)$$

identical to

$$A_{\square}(u_k) = \frac{\vartheta_1'(0)\vartheta_1(u_0 - \sum_{i=1,2,3} u_i) \prod_{(i,j)=1,2,3} \vartheta_1(u_i - u_j)}{\prod_{i=1,2,3} \vartheta_1^3(u_0 - u_i)} \quad (0.46)$$

where $\zeta_0 = \zeta(u_0 - u_i)$, $\wp_0 = \wp(u_0 - u_i)$.

Integrating from u_0, ζ_0, \wp_0 to u_i, ζ_i, \wp_i where $\zeta_i = \zeta(u_i)$, $\wp_i = \wp(u_i)$ one has

$$A[1, u, \zeta, \wp] = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ 1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ 1 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ 1 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ 1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ 1 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ 1 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} \prod M(\mathbf{a}) = 0 \quad (0.47)$$

A non-trivial solution exists also for non-equidistant and collinear iterations u_i , i.e. the set of solutions of a rank four condition (0.47) overwhelms that of a determinant $\det \zeta(u_i + u_j)$ of rank N being the usual addition theorem.

QCF $u_i \leftarrow \prod M(\mathbf{a}) u_i$ in (0.47) contain a λ -dependent term (0.16) which is equivalent

to a quadratic field $M \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ due to continued fractions $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} = \prod M(\mathbf{a}) = \prod \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & a \end{pmatrix}$. Then (0.47) creates maximal four CM period scaled layer of

homogeneous \wp - functions with $M_d \in \mathbb{Q}[\sqrt{\Delta}]$ ($d=1,2,3,4$) on $\delta\mathbb{X}$

$$A[M, u, \zeta, \wp] = \begin{vmatrix} M_0 & u_0 & \zeta_0 & \wp_0 \\ M_1 & u_1 & \zeta_1 & \wp_1 \\ M_2 & u_2 & \zeta_2 & \wp_2 \\ M_3 & u_3 & \zeta_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} \prod M(\mathbf{a}) = 0 \quad (0.48)$$

Invariants (0.16) in (0.47) have small but finite statistical weight. As an addition quantum the ϑ_1 product in (0.45) remains valid by replacing $u_i \leftarrow \prod M(\mathbf{a}) u_i$ leading to a contour C_M .

Multiplying u by $\frac{\pi}{KK'}$, adding u and ζ - values in $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ yields $A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$

with the Heuman Lambda function $\Lambda(u) = \frac{\pi}{KK'} + \zeta(u)$

$$A[M, u, \Lambda, \wp] = \begin{vmatrix} M_0 & u_0 & \Lambda_0 & \wp_0 \\ M_1 & u_1 & \Lambda_1 & \wp_1 \\ M_2 & u_2 & \Lambda_2 & \wp_2 \\ M_3 & u_3 & \Lambda_3 & \wp_3 \end{vmatrix} \prod M(\mathbf{a}) = 0 \quad (0.49).$$

The quartic invariant (0.42) should be related to $\det A(M, u, \zeta, \wp) = 0$ of rank four.

$A[M, u, \zeta, \wp]$ is viewed as equivalent to 5- sphere orthogonality matrix $A[\delta a, \delta p]$, to spherical triangles on the unit sphere S^2 via the Weierstrass relation for $\sum \sigma(u_0)$ $\sigma(u_1)\sigma(u_2)\sigma(u_3)$ (see Appendix 1).

Point addition

$$x_1 = x_k = p(u_k), \quad x_2 = x_{k+1} = p(u_{k+1}), \quad x_3 = x_{k+2} = p(u_{k+2} = u_k \mp u_{k+1})$$

results from substituting from four roots of an invariant equation. Fractional substitutions $x \rightarrow F(\gamma_{\phi} \circ t, \gamma_{\phi} \circ x) \rightarrow F(t, x)$ leave elementary symmetric polynomials (0.42) invariant. Next (0.43) is consistent with an EQ polynomial $\sigma_2=0$ leading to $\sigma_4=0$ and

$$4A_1 \sum_1 A_2^3 \sum_2^3 + A_2^4 \sum_2^4 = 0 \quad (0.50)$$

having solution $y = \frac{A_2 \sum_2}{A_1 \sum_1} = (-4)^{\frac{1}{3}}$.

Collineations will be demonstrated for EQ E_λ leading to M_c, L_r and $SE(1)$ dynamics of the Lyapunov exponent in I. Invariant equation (0.50) is a conjugate map to EQ $\lambda=1^{1/3}$.

Appendix 3 Transition from robot dynamics to chaotic dynamics

Unimodular collineations $M(\mathbf{a})$ are generalized to n dimensions as continued fractions (CF) for n=1, bifurcating continued fractions (BCF) for n=2 and chaotic continued fractions (CCF) or quaternary continued fractions (QCF) for n=3

$$M(a_n) = \hat{t}_{n+1} + \begin{pmatrix} 0_{1,n} & 0 \\ 0_{n,n} & a_n^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (0.51)$$

with a zero matrix $0_{n,m}$ of n rows and m columns, $a_n=(a_1, \dots, a_n)$, a cyclic matrix \hat{t}_{n+1} of order n+1

($\hat{t}_{n+1}^{n+1} = 1, \hat{t}_{n+1} \hat{t}_{n+1}^T = 1$). Introducing the exponential map

$$t_{n+1}^T M(a_n) = G(R, a_n) = \begin{pmatrix} R & a_n \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_{n,n} & a_n^T \\ 0_{1,n} & 1 \end{pmatrix} = e^{S(a_n)}. \quad (0.52)$$

for $S(a_n) = \begin{pmatrix} R & a_n \\ 0_{n,1} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ satisfying $S^4 - R^2 S^2 = 0$ and $R^2 < 0$

Unimodular collineations $M(\mathbf{a})$ result from a cyclic shift of $G(R, \mathbf{a})$ for special Euclidian $SE(3)$ group and variables $x = (\mathbf{a}, 1) \in \mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}, p)$.

Nilpotent N_0 ($N_0^2 = 0$) and idempotent P_p for $p=0, \mp$ ($P_p^2 = P_p$) are

$$N_0 = \frac{1}{R^2} S^2 (R - S^2) \text{ and } P_0 = 1 - \frac{S^2}{R^2}, P_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2R^3} S^2 (R \mp S).$$

$M(\mathbf{a})$ is given by $\det M(a) = \det e^S = \det R = \det(P_0 + N_0 + e^{-R} P_+ + e^R P_-)$ and $e^S = P_0 + N_0 + e^{-R} P_+ + e^R P_-$

An $M(\mathbf{a}) - G(R, \mathbf{a})$ isomorphism of collineation $M(\mathbf{a})$ and $SE(3)$ steps in $\mathbb{S}^2(\mathbf{a}, p)$

requires four steps $\prod_{k=1, \dots, 4} R_k > 0$ where

$$\prod_{k=1}^4 \begin{pmatrix} R_k & \mathbf{x} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} R_1 R_2 R_3 R_4 & R_1 R_2 (R_3 + 1) \mathbf{a} + (R_1 + 1) \mathbf{a} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

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